

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D11.3 — Summary of EOSC-Life Main Achievements and Impacts with Sustainability and Exploitation Plans

WP11 – Project Management
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Executive Summary

Biological and Medical research directly addresses key societal challenges and drives the bioeconomy. Ensuring that Europe remains an international leader in life science research and continues to advance the understanding of life and disease requires that research data and digital services are findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable (FAIR), regardless of scientific discipline and national boundaries. In EOSC-Life the 13 Biological and Medical Research Infrastructures in Europe join forces to create an open collaborative digital space for the life sciences in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

EOSC-Life was designed and delivered as a user-driven project with driver projects identified through competitive, peer-reviewed open calls. An inclusive, collaborative approach and dedicated capacity building efforts fostered data science skills needed to adopt advanced data management practice and access data integration and large-scale analysis tools in the cloud.

This deliverable describes how EOSC-Life established advanced data services, technology platforms, and support services within EOSC and established toolkits that allow data from within the European Research Area to be accessible for reuse in EOSC in full compliance with all ethical, regulatory, and legal requirements. The deliverable summarises the results and achievements across all work packages in EOSC-Life and aims to provide a high-level narrative guide to project outcomes alongside the “EOSC-Life achievements brochure”¹.

Project Objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following Project objectives:

- a. Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources for cloud use.
- b. Create an ecosystem of innovative life-science tools in EOSC.
- c. Enable ground-breaking data driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Introduction

The EOSC-Life project brought together the 13 research infrastructures in the *Health and Food domain* of the ESFRI Roadmap (the Life Science research infrastructures, LS RI) to develop the life science component of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The other ESFRI domains have

¹ The brochure is available via the EOSC-Life webpage: <https://www.eosc-life.eu/achievements/>

delivered similar projects and collectively these research infrastructure driven projects are referred to as the *Science clusters*.

Domain	EOSC cluster project	URL
Particle physics & Astronomy	ESCAPE	https://projectescape.eu/
Social Sciences & Humanities	SSHOC	https://sshopencloud.eu/
Environmental & Climate	ENVRI-FAIR	https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/
Photon and Neutron sources	PaNOSC	https://www.panosc.eu/
Life Sciences / Health & Food	EOSC-Life	https://www.eosc-life.eu/

Table 1: The EOSC Science Cluster projects

The ambition of the science cluster projects is to establish the means, in terms of data, technology and people, that would allow RIs to participate fully in EOSC, and thus deliver benefit to their users. In the case of EOSC-Life, the target is the life science research community in Europe.

ESFRI Research infrastructures are user focused organisations, established with the purpose of making advanced science facilities accessible to scientists throughout the European Research Area. The LS RI provide Europe's researchers with access to the samples, data and research facilities needed for modern life science research such as advanced imaging and phenotyping facilities, biobanks, research stations in unique ecosystems and clinical trials. Typically, this user access is through *open access infrastructure* with no limitations on use by science and society (e.g., open data resources, catalogues, registries) or access via *excellence-driven open calls* (e.g., access to advanced imaging or phenotyping and screening facilities). EOSC-Life has been a user-driven project and access to project outcomes has been provided through both routes: many of the project outcomes are established as open access services (e.g., workflow registries, ontology lookup services, user login and authorisation services). Importantly, these services were developed in close partnership with our user community – engaged via a series of open calls.

The project's ambition to create an EOSC for the life sciences built on data and technology capabilities operated by qualified staff in the life science research infrastructures. Consequently, the project sustainability and exploitation plans were rooted in the individual LS RI operations. The research infrastructures are long-term stable entities, participating in a wide range of national and European projects, and so embedding the developed capabilities in the individual research infrastructures provides a foundation for further development, effective life-cycle management, and user exploitation.

This deliverable summarises the EOSC-Life outcomes (often called “key exploitable results” in the EOSC terminology) and provides an overview of the plans for long-term sustainability and exploitation of the assets. The latter is also addressed specifically in a publication submitted for publication and summarised in Deliverable D1.4 “EOSC Sustainability best practice”².

² Pre-print published here: <https://zenodo.org/record/8247376>

2. EOSC-Life outcomes

For the summary of project outcomes provided in this deliverable we classify the EOSC-Life outcomes in:

1. RI and People capabilities – “Readiness for EOSC and interdisciplinary collaboration”
2. Cross-RI user access and support – “EOSC in practice”
3. Consolidated data and computational services – “Populating EOSC”

The outcomes of EOSC-Life have been continuously reported on the EOSC-Life website in a “tiled” format³. Each tile represents a specific outcome – “key exploitable result” and can be individually hyperlinked and so easily communicated and accessed (e.g., in RI newsletters or in an email as response to a user question). The system also allows the use of “QR-codes” to provide direct access via a familiar smartphone interface:

Science Demonstrators

EOSC-Life funded 8 “Demonstrator” projects representing novel cloud deployments from participating RIs. These scientific and technical use cases guided and structured the work done in EOSC-Life, showing how an open digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research can be built. Covering a broad scope of life science domains, these projects made new data, tools, and workflows available in the cloud for re-use by the scientific community. The publications and resources, including training material and documentation, are openly accessible.

Figure 1: Example use of QR code for dissemination of project outcomes

The EOSC-Life outcomes were documented at the mid-term with publication of the first version of the “EOSC-Life achievements brochure”:

Figure 2: Mid-term EOSC-Life achievement⁴

³ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/achievements/>

⁴ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/eosc-life-achievements-brochure-Final.pdf>

This brochure has been updated for project finalisation and is provided online via the achievement page of the EOSC-Life webpage.

While the EOSC-Life website, deliverables and brochures provide the complete documentation of project outcomes the paragraphs below aim to provide an accessible summary as context and background for the rest of this deliverable.

2.1 RI and People capabilities – “Readiness for EOSC and interdisciplinary collaboration”

Many scientists will interface with the EOSC through research infrastructures – from the perspective of EOSC the LS RI are “intermediaries” that support users with e.g., FAIR data management or access to advanced analytics capabilities as they are accessing the RI services or facilities. Thus, a key ambition for EOSC-Life was to build data capacity and knowledge in each of the LS RI. In the design of EOSC-Life resources were set aside such that each of the infrastructures could hire a “data expert” aligned with the key issues facing the respective RI (e.g., in case of ECRIN aligned with clinical trial data/metadata repositories and sensitive data). These data experts have been the primary contact points between the RIs in the project and in many cases also served as the interface to the wider EOSC ecosystem. The current LS RI membership of the EOSC Association is: EATRIS, ERINHA, BBMRI-ERIC, Euro-BioImaging ERIC, ELIXIR/EMBL.

At the start of EOSC-Life the data capabilities and knowledge of EOSC was highly variable within the LS RI; some infrastructures have long-standing, advanced data capabilities and had been part of the initial EOSC planning and piloting phases – other LS RI were newly launched and had very little capacity established. As such the initial focus of EOSC-Life training efforts was towards the RI operators, managers, and other staff to build the foundational skills needed for successful project execution. This was achieved through e-learning, training courses and, most importantly, a series of collaborative “FAIR Hackathons” where hands-on support and development was provided by the RIs with established data capabilities (see the EOSC-Life training page⁵ for details on the courses and content). The internal capacity building has continued throughout the project lifetime with progressively advanced topics being introduced – for instance in the last year of the project EOSC-Life has provided access to highly technical training in cloud deployment and “DevOps” practices for RI staff. The capacity and people developments efforts has also included non-technical capabilities with workshops on integration of gender dimensions in research as well as a comprehensive programme for developing the internal RI training capabilities (e.g., “train-the-trainer and documenting training impact). In response to the COVID-19 pandemic and the transition to remote access modalities the project developed and delivered support for remote training and knowledge exchange (e.g., “transfer to remote delivery”, “hosting hybrid events”, “remote access procedures) to the LS RIs. The overall training programme outcome and impact is summarised in D9.3 *Final report on EOSC-Life training activities and their impact*⁶.

Interdisciplinarity is at the heart of EOSC - a stated aim of the EOSC programme is to create a “multi-disciplinary environment where researchers can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services, enabling them to better conduct their work”. EOSC-Life has closely collaborated with the

⁵ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/services/training/>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8083413>

other science clusters, informally to create a network of contacts across the disciplines and more formally to publish a series of joint white papers and position statements on how to support and develop science-focussed, transdisciplinary services in EOSC (Table 1.2, also summarised on the webpage⁷).

Publication	URL
Fostering Open Science with Science Clusters of ESFRI research infrastructures through both community-based and interdisciplinary projects and common actions	https://www.eosc-life.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/SCLS_infraeosc_HE_Destination_170921.pdf
ESFRI Science Clusters - Position Statement on Expectations and Long-Term Commitments in Open Science	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4889503
ESFRI Cluster Projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contribution to the EOSC	https://zenodo.org/record/3675081
EOSC - a tool for enabling Open Science in Europe	https://zenodo.org/record/4044010#.X5KTqIgzUk

The outcome of this cross-cluster collaboration is visible in several transdisciplinary collaborative projects, for instance the cross-cluster “science cases” in the EOSC Future project⁸, the incorporation of social science data in the COVID-19 data portal via the BY-COVID project⁹ and the new EVERSE and OSCARS projects that will start in 2024 and focus on reproducible research software and transdisciplinary service provision respectively.

2.2 Cross-RI user access and support – “EOSC in practice”

The goal of the open calls was to facilitate co-creation of an open, digital collaborative space for life science research by developing FAIR tools, workflows, resources, infrastructures, and guidelines in a collaboration between with the EOSC-Life RIs experts and representatives of life-science research communities. The direct outcomes of the open call project are reported in D3.3 *Report on the work of the Open Call Projects*¹⁰, here we focus on a couple of additional outcomes of the open call programme.

A novel aspect of the EOSC-Life open call process was the introduction of a “project maturation phase” (D3.3, Section 1.3). During initial consultation with users and based on the experiences from the “demonstrator projects” (D3.2) it was recognised that many users did not have the data and technical skills needed to write effective proposals for project partnering. The maturation approach was developed in response to this skills gap – during the maturation phase applicants

⁷ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/resources/project-deliverables/>

⁸ <https://eoscfuture.eu/data-in-action/>

⁹ <https://by-covid.eu/news-events/by-covid-data-indexing-system/>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8263073>

had access to project experts for consultation and support to shape technically feasible proposals that draw on the capabilities of multiple RI. In addition, the RI services are often technically and scientifically complex and so the maturation phase mitigates at two additional challenges: first, the inherent bias against new users since returning users have a good understanding of the technologies and so can write tailored proposals and secondly, the challenge of developing projects benefiting from multiple RI facilities – which needs support of technical experts from multiple organisations to develop feasible projects. An important outcome of EOSC-Life is this experience in shaping effective user access programmes for EOSC (D3.3, Section 3, 3. *Lessons learned - Recommendation for future Open Calls*) which will inform e.g., the OSCARS project¹¹.

Additionally, EOSC-Life Open Call programmes have supported the development of cross-RI capabilities for user access: WP3 was delivered in a close collaboration between user-access officers from several research infrastructures. As such, cluster projects such as EOSC-Life provide both drivers and resources to build capacity and harmonisation of procedures between the participating research infrastructures. As the LS RI now are involved in a portfolio of transnational access projects (e.g., ISIDORE¹², AgroServ¹³, canSERV¹⁴) this experience directly benefit the RI users and provide an additional benefit of EOSC investments into the European Research Area. Notably the “ARIA” software¹⁵ for user access management (WP5), and the BBMRI’s Negotiator¹⁶, are used by RIs in these transnational access programmes.

2.3 Consolidated data and computational services – “Populating EOSC”

The EOSC-Life ambition of an “open collaborative space for digital biology” rests on a technical foundation. The project has developed and delivered a set of consolidated services for FAIR data, user access management and for data analysis in the cloud. These services, together with the long-term sustainability plans are described in a preprint and submitted for publication¹⁷. Table 1 from the preprint is reproduced below for reference and lists the project “Key Exploitable Results”.

These consolidated data, user access and computational services represents the tangible part of “EOSC for the life sciences” – together with the more intangible skills and practices described above they form the basis for bringing EOSC to life science researchers in Europe. Importantly, the user call projects (above, D3.3) provides prospective users with a catalogue of exemplar applications that help scientists understand how to effectively engage with EOSC (see exploitation below). The services will, funding permitting, be maintained by the LS RI as part of on-going operations (see section 3, Sustainability, below). Many of the developed services have already

¹¹ The OSCARS project brings together all the science clusters under the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01 call and is at the moment in Grant Agreement Preparations.

¹² <https://isidore-project.eu/>

¹³ <https://agroserv.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.canserv.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://instruct-eric.org/help/about-aria>

¹⁶ <https://negotiator.bbmri-eric.eu/login.xhtml>

¹⁷ David, R.; Rybina, A.; Burel, J.-M. *et al.* (2023). “Be Sustainable Recommendations” for FAIR Resources in Life Sciences research: EOSC-Life’s Lessons” (preprint). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8247376>

been incorporated into national and European projects, including a new wave of EOSC projects (e.g., EOSC4Cancer¹⁸, BY-COVID¹⁹, EuroScienceGateway²⁰, OSCARS²¹, EOSC-ENTRUST²²).

Table-1. Key Exploitable Results from EOSC-Life used by communities (<i>Life Sciences Data Resources & Tools, harmonisation of Access & Policies - in EOSC</i>)		
Result	URL	Description
<i>I. LS Data in EOSC: FAIR LS data resources for cloud use (organisational sustainability, technical sustainability, sustainable access to data, sustainable data governance)</i>		
COVID-19 Portal	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.f3b7a9	Resources focusing on COVID-19-related data
Common Provenance Model	https://fairsharing.org/4610	Standard based on W3C PROV, which allows publishing, finding & interlinking provenance information in distributed environments
Clinical Trial Data Repository	https://fairsharing.org/3067	Portal allows users to search for studies using a variety of criteria and identify the data objects associated with them
Ontology Lookup Service (OLS)	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.Mkl9RR	Repository for biomedical ontologies that aims to provide a single point of access to the latest ontology versions
Ontology Cross Reference Service (OxO)	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0c6fea	Database of ontology cross-references (or xrefs)
Sensitive data toolbox	https://fairsharing.org/3577	Open, digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research, across LS RIs
<i>II. LS Toolkits in EOSC: eco-system of innovative LS tools and key services/standards in EOSC (sustainability through re-use, technical sustainability)</i>		
FAIRsharing	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2abis5	Resource on (meta)data standards, inter-related to databases and data policies

¹⁸ <https://eosc4cancer.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://by-covid.eu/>

²⁰ <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/>

²¹ Project in GA preparations

²² Project in GA preparations

Workflowhub	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.07cf72	Registry for publishing scientific computational workflows
Schema.org	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hzdqz8	Community activity handling schemas for structured data
Bioschemas.org	https://fairsharing.org/3517	LS branch of Schema.org, aims to improve data interoperability in LS
RO-Crate	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wUoZKE	Community effort focusing on packaging research data with metadata, complementing richer metadata standards
FAIR Cookbook	https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org	Recipes for the FAIRification journey
Galaxy	https://galaxyproject.org/eu/	Open-Source project for FAIR data analysis
Scipion (workflows)	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.EsY1WF	Cryo-EM image processing framework
BAND	https://band.embl.de	Virtual Desktop for bioimage analysis in the cloud
RDMKit	https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/	Best practices and guidelines to help you make your data FAIR
III. Harmonisation of Access and Policies across the LS (RIs)		
LS Login	https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login.html	Common Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) system for LS RIs and communities
ARIA	https://aria.services/	User access management system (AMS)
Open Calls Procedures	https://zenodo.org/record/4048442	Guidelines for organising, running and integrating Open Calls and user projects into EOSC framework

3. EOSC-Life Sustainability

EOSC-Life strategy for sustainability and long-term life-cycle management was set out at the outset: all services and procedures that require on-going maintenance would be associated with a lead RI that takes responsibility for orchestrating their use and maintenance.

In addition, the project commitment to open science provides a solid foundation for community-driven sustainability: all data, software and tools are released with open source/open data licenses. Hence, future support can be organised with resources from multiple institutions and

project consortia – the open science licensing avoids lengthy negotiations on intellectual property, access to project background and so promotes reuse and collaborative uptake and development. For instance, WorkflowHub.eu was originally conceived and developed by partners in EOSC-Life WP2. The development was accelerated during the COVID-19 pandemic to provide a hub for reproducible analytics workflows and the registry is now in active use by a range of projects and research infrastructures that all contribute resources to the long-term maintenance.

Figure 3: The workflowhub.eu is now used and developed through multiple projects and organisations, attracting funding from EC as well as national funding agencies in DE, UK, CH, and NL demonstrating the power of Open Science as a driver for long-term sustainability.

EOSC-Life sustainability planning was initiated at the March 2022 AGM with a project-wide “world café” session that captured all outcomes and exploitable results together with the responsible RI partner. The resulting spreadsheet was used as a basis for the work package driven sustainability planning that informed a final set of joint priorities, agreed by the directors of the 13 LS RI. These joint priorities informed the proposed participation of the LS RI in EOSC related calls. The overall sustainability planning is summarised in D1.4 and the lessons learnt from EOSC-Life are disseminated in the associated preprint described above (David et al, 2023, submitted). Notably, the development of the sustainability paper was driven by an Open Science Radical Collaboration Approach pioneered by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) (David et al, 2023, submitted).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
1	Name of person adding the item	Output / Product / Deliverable	To whom does it matter?	Why does it matter to them? What problem was it solving?	Additional information	What questions do you still have?	WP / Contact persons for various stakeholders	Additional comment
2		MICHA - FAIRifying drug sensitivity screening data	Professionals in High Throughput screening	Standardisation of chromosensitivity assay (meta)data	Call for action: submit data xyz	Does it also include low throughput data?	WP1, EU-OpenScreen, EATNS	
3		Strategies for cloud hosting/data integration/analysis/lessons/strategy derived from EOSC-Life open call projects/partners	1. Resource developers 2. Funders 3. EOSC	Transition to cloud hosting, making EOSCLife outputs tangible	A series of collected brief articles, either published in a journal as an output or perhaps hosted on a blog site or other open science. The aim is to extract value from Open Call projects and to disseminate them to develop - animation / helpdesk / short training on how to use it.	Will this be widely useful as a complement to regular publications and training articles?	WP1, 2, 3 partners, WP7 also.	
4		COVID 19 Data repository	Clinical researchers	access to individual participant data, that otherwise has a use limited to the initial study in which the participant was enrolled; encourage reuse of critical data			WP14 - ECRIN	
5		Domain specific FAIR guidelines/metadata schema	Domain specialists, others wanting to implement FAIR principles at a domain level	Guide for FAIR data deposition, improvement of data sharing, help for domains at the start of the FAIR implementation journey.	Community review of guidelines - open review to also be published, case study to be published in FAIR cookbook	Where is best to archive metadata schema for others to use? we will have it linked to a paper and on zenodo but does it need to be elsewhere? - generalised metadata schema	WP3,	
6		ARIA for use in access and other research infrastructure calls	It matters to all research infrastructure managers looking for a tool to manage their access nodes, training or other calls. Also to any access project in particular the ones with complex partnership to provide appropriate support	Providing access is a complex activity that needs expert software support	https://instruct-eric.eu/help/about-aria	What are the main issues that ARIA doesn't cover that we need to work on	WP5 WP9 C E C	
7		Common Provenance Model & developed ISO 23474 provenance standard	researchers/industry (users of research outputs) - to support reproducibility of experiments and traceability and quality/fitness-for-purpose assessment of used objects (e.g. datasets, biological samples); developers/industry - to enable the developed tools/devices generate provenance information in accordance with the proposed model; government/funders - the proposed provenance standard will increase value returned for funded research				WP6	

Figure 4: Example outcomes (row 1-7 of 50) from the EOSC-Life World Café on sustainability. Names and other personal data have been redacted in the image. The 2022 sessions provided an effective basis and joint approach across the work packages.

A second pillar of EOSC-Life sustainability is provided by the cross-cluster work (Section 3.2.1) with the joint positioning and common strategies for provisioning of research infrastructure driven services in the EOSC. For instance, EOSC-Life established a collaboration with EOSC-Nordic

to broaden the user-base (and associated community support) for service delivery²³ and the informal discussions and alignment between ESCAPE and EOSC-Life experts on good practices for high-end scientific software led to a joint, cross-community project proposal for long-term robust, reproducible and sustainable software development practices (the EVERSE project being in GA preparations and planned to start in 2024).

4. Future exploitation and service delivery in EOSC

The ongoing delivery of FAIR data services to the life science community in the context of EOSC rests on their exploitation through the established LS RI services

The EOSC-Life open call projects provide a solid basis for future exploitation, as the services were developed with diverse user communities, they were ready to be deployed in additional contexts. In addition, the successful delivery of tools that were demonstrable useful helped to engage new user communities and attract other partners.

The collaborative data, user and analysis services developed in EOSC-Life are being taken forward, via their lead RI, into new projects and initiatives. Together with the Open Science based sustainability strategy (Section 3.3) this gives a solid basis for continued service operations.

Figure 5: Example EOSC-Life services that now are underpinning service delivery in a range of new projects.

One example on this continued service delivery is the EOSC-Life work on provenance standards to enhance reproducibility and trust in computational sciences (D6.2²⁴). The work was initiated under CORBEL (the LS RI cluster project preceding EOSC-Life), continued in EOSC-Life and is now published as an ISO standard²⁵. The on-going dissemination and exploitation of this standard has been carried forward by the team, led by BBMRI-ERIC, in projects such as BY-COVID.

²³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8114776>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4705073>

²⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/80715.html>

The LS RI also benefit, and continue to exploit, the intangible outcomes of EOSC-Life. EOSC will be an important fixture of the future European data landscape and the collaborative capacity building of RI data expertise in EOSC-Life, e.g., the understanding EOSC, support the development of aligned data strategies between the LS RI. A good example of this is the shared data management plan developed by the two projects BY-COVID and ISIDORE launched in 2021 as part of the COVID emergency response. ISIDORE (led by ERINHA) provides transnational access for research into pathogens and pandemic preparedness (e.g., for COVID, mpox, and now other pathogens on WHO Blueprint²⁶). BY-COVID drives the continued development of the COVID-19 data portal and, building on EOSC-Life, the provision of pathogen-oriented data services within EOSC. To guide FAIR data management of a wide range of diverse datatypes the two projects developed and published an “umbrella” data management plan to guide FAIR practices at all the facilities. Notably, the network of LS RI data experts established in EOSC-Life was critical to this effort (David et al, 2023, Umbrella Data Management Plans to integrate FAIR data: Lessons from the ISIDORE and BY-COVID consortia for pandemic preparedness. Manuscript submitted for publication²⁷).

Many of the core data and computational services developed in EOSC-Life have applicability outside the life science domain and so cross-cluster collaboration is a natural avenue for their on-going exploitation. The EuroScienceGateway project²⁸ is a good example: Built around the well-established workflow services that formed the core of WP2, and including EOSC-Life developments such as workflowhub.eu, the project brings together use-cases from biodiversity, material science and astrophysics for continued development of the services in other domains alongside the life sciences.

Description of Work

This summary deliverable of achievements was drafted by project coordination based on input from work packages and reviewed by WP leads.

Delivery and schedule

The deliverable is delayed: No

Adjustments

Adjustments made: None

²⁶ <https://www.who.int/teams/blueprint/who-r-and-d-blueprint-for-epidemics>

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520086>

²⁸ <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/>

